

Vector Summary

Vector ID	VB241111-1111fuf
Vector Name	pLV[Exp]-EGFP/Neo-TRE>hATF5[NM_001193646.2]
Vector Size	9977 bp
Viral Genome Size	6150 bp
Vector Type	Mammalian Gene Expression Lentiviral Vector
Inserted Promoter	TRE
Inserted ORF	hATF5[NM_001193646.2]
Inserted Marker	EGFP/Neo
Plasmid Copy Number	High
Antibiotic Resistance	Ampicillin
Cloning Host	VB UltraStable (or alternative strain)

Vector Map

Vector Components

Name	Position	Size (bp)	Type	Description	Application notes
CMV promoter	■ 1-581	581	Promoter	Human cytomegalovirus immediate early enhancer/promoter	Strong promoter; may have variable strength in some cell types.
5' LTR-ΔU3	■ 582-762	181	LTR	Truncated HIV-1 5' long terminal repeat	Allows transcription of viral RNA and its packaging into virus.
Ψ	■ 873-917	45	Miscellaneous	HIV-1 packaging signal	Allows packaging of viral RNA into virus.
RRE	■ 1427-1660	234	Miscellaneous	HIV-1 Rev response element	Rev protein binding site that allows Rev-dependent nuclear export of viral RNA during viral packaging.
cPPT	■ 2152-2268	117	Miscellaneous	Central polypurine tract	Facilitates the nuclear import of HIV-1 cDNA through a central DNA flap.
TRE	■ 2336-2759	424	Promoter	Tetracycline-responsive element promoter (2nd generation)	Regulated by a class of transcription factors (e.g. tTA, rtTA and tTS) whose activities are dependent on tetracycline or its analogs (e.g. doxycycline).
Kozak	■ 2784-2789	6	Miscellaneous	Kozak translation initiation sequence	Facilitates translation initiation of ATG start codon downstream of the Kozak sequence.
hATF5[NM_001193646.2]	■ 2790-3638	849	CDS	<i>None</i>	<i>None</i>
WPRE	■ 3677-4274	598	Miscellaneous	Woodchuck hepatitis virus posttranscriptional regulatory element	Enhances virus stability in packaging cells, leading to higher titer of packaged virus; enhances higher expression of transgenes.
CMV promoter	■ 4296-4883	588	Promoter	Human cytomegalovirus immediate early enhancer/promoter	Strong promoter; may have variable strength in some cell types.

Name	Position	Size (bp)	Type	Description	Application notes
EGFP/Neo	■ 4915-6426	1512	CDS	EGFP fused with Neo	Allows cells to be visualized by green fluorescence and resistant to geneticin (G418).
3' LTR-ΔU3	■ 6497-6731	235	LTR	Truncated HIV-1 3' long terminal repeat	Allows packaging of viral RNA into virus; self-inactivates the 5' LTR by a copying mechanism during viral genome integration; contains polyadenylation signal for transcription termination.
SV40 early pA	■ 6804-6938	135	Regulatory Elements	Simian virus 40 early polyadenylation signal	Allows transcription termination and polyadenylation of mRNA transcribed by Pol II RNA polymerase.
Ampicillin	■ 7892-8752	861	CDS	Ampicillin resistance gene	Allows E. coli to be resistant to ampicillin.
pUC ori	■ 8923-9511	589	Rep_origin	pUC origin of replication	Facilitates plasmid replication in E. coli; regulates high-copy plasmid number (500-700).

Note: Components added by user are listed in **bold red** text.

Vector Sequence

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1  TAGTTATTAA TAGTAATCAA TTACGGGGTC ATTAGTTCAT AGCCCATATA TGGAGTTCCG CGTTACATAA
71  CTTACGGTAA ATGGCCCGCC TGGCTGACCG CCCAACGACC CCCGCCATT GACGTCAATA ATGACGTATG
141  TTCCCATAGT AACGCCAATA GGGACTTTCC ATTGACGTCA ATGGGTGGAG TATTTACGGT AAAGTCCCA
211  CTTGGCAGTA CATCAAGTGT ATCATATGCC AAGTACGCC CCTATTGACG TCAATGACGG TAAATGGCCC
281  GCCTGGCATT ATGCCAGTA CATGACCTTA TGGGACTTTC CTACTTGGCA GTACATCTAC GTATTAGTCA
351  TCGCTATTAC CATGGTGATG CGGTTTTGGC AGTACATCAA TGGGCGTGGG TAGCGGTTTG ACTCACGGGG
421  ATTTCCAAGT CTCCACCCCA TTGACGTCAA TGGGAGTTTG TTTTGGCACC AAAATCAACG GGACTTTCCA
491  AAATGTCGTA ACAACTCCGC CCCATTGACG CAAATGGGCG GTAGGCGTGT ACGGTGGGAG GTCTATATAA
561  GCAGAGCTGG TTTAGTGAAC CGGGTCTCTC TGGTTAGACC AGATCTGAGC CTGGGAGCTC TCTGGCTAAC
631  TAGGGAACCC ACTGCTTAAG CCTCAATAAA GCTTGCCTTG AGTGCTTCAA GTAGTGTGTG CCCGCTGTT
701  GTGTGACTCT GGTAAGTAGA GATCCCTCAG ACCCTTTTAG TCAGTGTGGA AAATCTCTAG CAGTGGCGCC
771  CGAACAGGGA CTTGAAAGCG AAAGGGAAAC CAGAGGAGCT CTCTCGACGC AGGACTCGGC TTGCTGAAGC
841  GCGCACGGCA AGAGGCGAGG GGCGGCGACT GGTGAGTACG CCAAAAATTT TGACTAGCGG AGGCTAGAAG

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911 GAGAGAGATG GGTGCAGAG CGTCAGTATT AAGCGGGGA GAATTAGATC GCGATGGGAA AAAATTCGGT
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 1051 CGCAGTTAAT CCTGGCCTGT TAGAAACATC AGAAGGCTGT AGACAAATAC TGGGACAGCT ACAACCATCC
 1121 CTTCAGACAG GATCAGAAGA ACTTAGATCA TTATATAATA CAGTAGCAAC CCTCTATTGT GTGCATCAAA
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 1961 AGGTTTAAGA ATAGTTTTTG CTGTACTTTC TATAGTGAAT AGAGTTAGGC AGGGATATTC ACCATTATCG
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 2241 AAAACAAATT ACAAAATTC AAAATTTTCG GGTTTATTAC AGGGACAGCA GAGATCCAGT TTATCGAGGC
 2311 TAGCCAATT TGTATAGAAA AGTTGGGTAC CGAGCTCGAC TTTCACTTTT CTCTATCACT GATAGGGAGT
 2381 GGTAACTCG ACTTTCACTT TTCTCTATCA CTGATAGGGA GTGGTAAACT CGACTTTCAC TTTTCTCTAT
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 9801 AATTGTGAGC GGATAACAAT TTCACACAGG AAACAGCTAT GACCATGATT ACGCCAAGCG CGCAATTAAC
 9871 CCTCACTAAA GGAACAAAA GCTGGAGCTG CAAGCTT
 9941

Validation by Restriction Enzyme Digestion

Restriction Enzymes	Cutting Sites	DNA Fragments (bp)
NheI	[2310]	[9977]
SpeI	[4314]	[9977]
ApaI	[3891, 8008, 9254]	[4117, 1246, 4614]
AvrII	[7099]	[9977]
DraIII	[7540]	[9977]

Restriction Enzymes	Cutting Sites	DNA Fragments (bp)
ApaI+NheI	[2310, 3891, 8008, 9254]	[1581, 4117, 1246, 3033]
ApaI+SpeI	[3891, 4314, 8008, 9254]	[423, 3694, 1246, 4614]
ApaI+AvrII	[3891, 7099, 8008, 9254]	[3208, 909, 1246, 4614]
ApaI+DraIII	[3891, 7540, 8008, 9254]	[3649, 468, 1246, 4614]